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AN ADAPTIVE UPSCALING APPROACH FOR ASSESSING MATERIALS' CIRCULARITY POTENTIAL WITH NON-DESTRUCTIVE TESTING (NDT)

Ghezal Ahmad Jan Zia¹, Christoph Völker², Benjamín Moreno Torres³, and Sabine Kruschwitz⁴

¹ Dr, Bundesanstalt für Materialforschung und -prüfung, ghezal-ahmad.zia@bam.de

² Dr, Bundesanstalt für Materialforschung und -prüfung, christoph.voelker@bam.de

³ MSc, Technische Universität Berlin, benjamin.moreno.torres@tu-berlin.de

⁴ Prof. Dr., Bundesanstalt für Materialforschung und -prüfung and Technische Universität Berlin, sabine.kruschwitz@bam.de

ABSTRACT

Advancing towards a circular economy necessitates the efficient reuse and maintenance of structural materials, which relies on accurate, non-damaging condition assessments. This paper introduces an innovative AI-driven adaptive sampling (AS) technique integrated with Non-Destructive Testing (NDT) to optimize this process. AS focuses on critical data points, reducing the amount of data needed for precise assessments—evidenced by our method requiring on average only 7 samples for Logistic Regression and 8 for Random Forest, contrasted with 29 for traditional sampling.

By reducing the necessity for extensive data collection, our method not only streamlines the assessment process but also significantly contributes to the sustainability goals of the circular economy. These goals include resource efficiency, waste reduction, and material reuse. Efficient condition assessments promote infrastructure longevity, reducing the need for new materials and the associated environmental impact.

The circular economy aims to create a sustainable system where resources are reused, and waste is minimized. This is achieved by extending the lifecycle of materials, reducing the environmental footprint, and promoting recycling and reuse. Longevity directly contributes to the circular economy by maximizing the utility and lifespan of existing materials and structures. Longer-lasting infrastructure means fewer resources are needed for repairs or replacements, leading to reduced material consumption and waste generation. This aligns with the circular economy's principles of sustainability and resource efficiency. This research not only advances the field of structural health monitoring but also aligns with the broader objective of enhancing sustainable construction practices within the circular economy framework.

Keywords: *Adaptive Sampling, Random Sampling, Machine Learning, Non-Destructive Testing, Condition Assessment, Circular Economy.*

Ghezal Ahmad Jan Zia

Unter den Eichen 87, Berlin, Germany, 12205

Email: ghezal-ahmad.zia@bam.de | **Tel:** +49 30 8104-4584 | **Web:** www.bam.de

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1. INTRODUCTION

The pursuit of sustainability in the construction sector is increasingly guided by the principles of the circular economy, which promotes resource reuse and optimization to prolong the lifespan of materials and structures. In a circular economy, the goal is to create a closed-loop system where materials are continuously cycled back into use, minimizing waste and the need for new raw materials. This approach is critical in the construction sector, where extending the lifespan of buildings and their components directly reduces the environmental impact and resource consumption.

NDT methods for concrete assessment have become a widely adopted practice [1]. However, the extensive data collection required for these methods, which often involves scanning a close-meshed grid, poses a major challenge, especially in the case of large structures or limited resources. The traditional answer has been automation through robotic data collection [2], but scalability and resource optimization issues remain.

Adaptive sampling (AS) addresses these challenges by using a predictive model to smartly navigate data collection based on past data, thus optimizing efficiency, and maintaining accurate detection with minimal data collection [3]. Studies such as those by [4] and [5] have demonstrated the efficacy of AS in environmental monitoring and image recognition. In addition, AS's ability to dynamically adjust data collection and reduce data needs while preserving accuracy is particularly beneficial for large-scale and resource-limited projects [6].

This investigation addresses a critical research gap: can AS, already being successful in various fields, be effectively applied to NDT in construction to provide a reliable and cost-efficient alternative to traditional methods? Answering this could advance NDT techniques, supporting sustainable construction aligned with circular economy objectives.

Despite its advantages, the application of AS in conjunction with NDT in construction is underexplored, highlighting a significant research opportunity. Here, material degradation, for instance, due to moisture ingress or cracking, is often highly localized. Given the large structure surfaces, it can be challenging to identify areas of interest. Integrating AS with NDT could enhance detection efficiency, lower data collection costs, and improve scalability, making it a promising area for future research [7]. Our research presents an innovative approach that integrates AS with multi-sensor NDT measurement data from the literature [8], namely half-cell potential, microwave moisture evaluation, and Wenner resistivity, specifically targeting mechanisms like pitting corrosion in reinforced concrete slabs –localized damage making distant data less relevant.

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1.3 Hypothesis and Research Question

We hypothesize that integrating AS with artificial intelligence (AI) algorithms in NDT significantly improves the efficiency of condition assessments across large construction areas. This improvement is evidenced by a reduction in the number of samples needed to detect corrosion, with detection rates substantially exceeding those achieved through traditional methods and statistical techniques like random sampling. To validate this hypothesis, we will address two key research questions (RQs):

RQ1: Effectiveness of Adaptive Sampling: How does the efficiency of AI-driven AS in detecting corrosion compare to traditional random sampling methods, especially for small and localized damage areas?

RQ2: Impact of Sampling Strategy Configuration: What effects do various sampling strategy configurations have on the efficiency and outcomes of AS in NDT??

The first question investigates whether AS can match or exceed the detection rates of corrosion achieved by random sampling, evaluating its potential to transform condition assessments across expansive construction surfaces. The second question examines the impact of selecting different machine learning models. Understanding how these configurations influence AS's effectiveness and resource demands is crucial for assessing its practicality and scalability in real-world infrastructure evaluations.

2. RESEARCH METHODS

In the following we describe how the AS is implemented with NDT measurements, the benchmarking procedure, and the underlying NDT data are taken from Völker et al. 2018 [9].

2.1 AI-driven Adaptive Sampling

AS method supported by AI strategically selects subsequent measurement points to improve detection efficiency, which is driven by an acquisition function. This function balances the probability of predicted corrosion with the uncertainty arising from the spatial distribution of previously validated measurement points and aims to optimize the information gain from each new data point.

At the heart of this approach are two components: the AI prediction model and the sampling model (see **Figure 1, a**). The prediction model is tasked with data fusion of raw measurement data and translates these values into probabilities that indicate the presence of corrosion. This initial analysis provides a basic predictive landscape on which the sampling model builds. The latter considers the probabilities generated by the prediction model and incorporates the spatial distribution of previous measurements to calculate two key metrics for the remaining measurement field: the estimated probability of corrosion occurrence and the associated

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prediction uncertainty. These metrics can be used to selectively highlight areas that have both, a high probability of corrosion and are characterized by considerable uncertainty due to sparse sampling of previous data in that region, thus systematically enriching the model's knowledge of the test field.

The workflow is shown in **(Figure 1, b)** and begins with initial sampling, where a small amount of preliminary data is collected in the measurement area using non-destructive testing methods. This data serves as input to the prediction model, which fuses the data to predict the probability of corrosion at these initial points. The sampling model then performs a spatial analysis and creates a spatial acquisition function. This function evaluates both the probability of corrosion and the associated uncertainty for unmeasured points with a utility, taking into account that areas further away from previously measured locations have greater uncertainty and therefore may be considered more useful in assessing corrosion condition. Subsequent measurement points are selected based on this calculated "utility". The utility-based sampling ensures that each new measurement helps to refine the sampling model's understanding of the corrosion landscape of the measurement area.

The iterative process of measurement and prediction continues, with the measurements from each new data point feeding back into the sampling model. This cycle repeats, gradually refining the spatial understanding and predictive accuracy of the model, until sampling completion, which is determined either by reaching a predefined number of iterations or by exhausting the measurement budget.

This AI-driven AS method enables a more targeted and efficient exploration of measurement areas through its intelligent integration of predictive and spatial analysis, which can aid the detection and understanding of degradation mechanisms. By prioritizing areas with high information value, the method optimizes the use of resources and represents a significant advance in the practical applicability of the methods.

2.2 Benchmarking Adaptive Sampling

The efficacy of the AS methodology was evaluated through its application to a dataset with predefined corrosion outcomes. The primary metric of interest was the number of measurements necessary to accurately identify the site of corrosion.

This evaluation was conducted under a variety of initial conditions selected at random, with the localization process repeated multiple times to generate a distribution of the measurements required for corrosion detection. Statistical analysis of this distribution was then performed, with a specific focus on the 90% quantile of the number of iterations needed across several trials. This quantile was selected as a robust comparison metric, representing the threshold below which 90% of the localization runs were completed (thereby exceeding only 10% of cases). It allows for the assessment of different AS configurations, including variations in

prediction models, by quantifying the iterations required for effective site localization in most cases.

Figure 1. Workflow of AS-benchmarking, iteratively samples a given surface to find corrosion (marked in red).

Furthermore, the performance of the AS approach was benchmarked against two alternative strategies: a comprehensive measurement of all potential sites and a random selection process where measurement points are chosen sequentially without prior data. It is important to note that the benchmarking aimed not at the models' precision but their efficiency in data collection in real-world scenarios. For detailed evaluations of model accuracy, readers are referred to the original study that forms the basis of this research.

2.3 Dataset – NDT Methods

The dataset derives from a controlled experiment by Völker et al. [9] designed to simulate various stages of corrosion in concrete structures, consisting of 18 distinct experiments conducted in two campaigns. It includes spatial coordinates, sensor-based readings, and a binary label indicating the presence of corrosion (See **Table 1**).

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Table 1: presents an overview of the dataset's composition.

(1)	Nr. of training datasets	9
(2)	Nr. of test datasets	2
(3)	Test set grid	9 x13cm field measurement
(4)	Measurements	Half-cell potential - rebar potential Half-cell potential - change of rebar potential Wenner-resistivity - electrical resistivity Microwave-moisture - relative moisture of concrete
(5)	Target	Find corrosion site (1 corrosion per test grid)

The original dataset was collected in two campaigns on two different samples. Throughout the experiment, the condition of the sample was changed in a controlled manner - from an initial reference condition to controlled moisture and salt ingress to the onset of corrosion at a predetermined location. (1) The first campaign comprises 9 experiments and was used in this study to train the corrosion classifier. (2) The benchmarks were performed with a test dataset from the second measurement campaign containing 2 experiments with corrosion. (3) The dataset was downsampled by interpolation to a grid of 9x13cm, which corresponds to a realistic measurement resolution in practice. (4) Four common NDT signal features were used to characterize the corrosion condition. These measurements were performed manually and are labor-intensive and time-consuming in practice. (5) In contrast, the target, the location of pitting corrosion, is very localized. The challenge is to identify these as quickly as possible.

3. EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

The experimental parameters (summarized in **Table 2**) and the experimental program employed in our study are detailed in the following.

Table 2. Parameters and values used in the AI-driven Adaptive Sampling approach.

Parameter	Value
Prediction Model	Logistic Regression (LR), Random Forest (RF)
Adaptive Sampling Model	Gaussian Process Regression (GPR)
Sampling Strategy	Based on prediction likelihood, uncertainty
Initial Sample Size	4

Prediction Model: For the task of corrosion detection within our AS framework, two classification models have been compared: RF [10] and LR [11]. Both models are widely recognized for their robustness and resilience against outliers and noisy training data, which are expected in this study due to the defect size at the lower sensitivity limit of the NDT methods. These models have been implemented using the scikit-learn library [12].

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Adaptive Sampling Model: The GPR model created using scikit learn [12] was applied iteratively to identify and evaluate locations with the highest uncertainty regarding corrosion presence. We utilized both isotropic and anisotropic kernels to investigate how the shape and orientation of the sampling region affect the AS process.

Sampling Strategy: The AS process is primarily driven by two key strategies: prediction likelihood and uncertainty. Prediction likelihood prioritizes the selection of samples based on their higher probability of exhibiting corrosion, enabling the model to focus on potentially critical areas. Uncertainty, on the other hand, targets samples for which the model's predictions are least confident. This approach helps in directing the learning process towards areas that would most improve the model's performance and understanding.

Initial Sampling and Subsequent Procedure: Initial sampling and subsequent procedure: The AS procedure initially starts with a set of 4 samples. These were randomly selected using Latin Hypercube Sampling (LHS) [13], ensuring that they did not contain the target area. These samples were fed into the predictive model to generate initial point estimates for the probability of corrosion at the sample locations. In the subsequent test procedure, the GPR uses these corrosion likelihoods and computes locations that are considered most informative for further sampling according to **Figure 1, b**.

Experimental Procedure: Our test procedure aims to analyze statistical performance across different sampling methods through repeated detection runs to identify corrosion sites, measuring success by the number of required measurements. We executed 30 Adaptive Sampling (AS) runs with varied initial samples to assess performance variability under different initial conditions. In our analysis, we focus on the lower bound performance that serves as a critical indicator for potential real-world applications. With this approach, the safety concept traditionally applied to materials is adapted and applied instead to the test criteria to focus on the reliability of assessment procedures for materials intended for reuse. In particular, we use the 90th percentile as a benchmark, which indicates a performance threshold that is undercut in only 10% of our experiments, emphasizing the practicality of these methods compared to conventional methods.

4. RESULTS

Figure 2 evaluates the efficiency of adaptive sampling methods compared to baseline methods, focusing on the lower bound of the required number of measurements for accurate corrosion site detection. The AS methods, RF+GPR and LR+GPR, significantly surpass random sampling, necessitating only an average of 8 and 7 samples, respectively. This performance is consistent, with a standard deviation of less than two across 30 runs, highlighting their reliability.

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In contrast, random sampling exhibits a lower efficiency, with a lower bound performance of 29 samples and a higher variability, indicated by a standard deviation of nearly 11 measurements. Despite this, random sampling is still four times more efficient than measuring the entire measurement field, which requires the collection of 117 measurements on the 10 by 10 cm² grid. Meanwhile, the AS methods demonstrate approximately 15 times greater efficiency compared to full field measurement. These findings highlight the substantial efficiency gains possible through targeted sampling strategies, enabling more effective identification of localized phenomena with fewer data points.

The remarkable success rate achieved by the AS algorithms with minimal iterations—a 90% probability of detection—illustrates the transformative potential these methods hold for NDT and structural health monitoring.

Figure 3. Performance of AS algorithms measured by the number of iterations required to achieve 90% success probability. The results represent the mean performance across two different datasets.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The study presented investigates the potential of combining AS with AI algorithms in NDT to enhance the efficiency of condition assessments in large construction areas. The hypothesis posited that this integration would lead to significant improvements, particularly in detecting

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corrosion, by reducing the number of samples required and achieving higher detection rates than traditional methods and random sampling.

Addressing the first research question (RQ1), the effectiveness of AI-driven AS compared to traditional random sampling methods, particularly for small and localized damage areas, was assessed. The findings indicate that AS, particularly when combined with RF and LR algorithms alongside GPR, significantly surpasses the efficiency of random sampling in detecting corrosion within reinforced concrete structures. The adaptive sampling methods, RF+GPR and LR+GPR, required substantially fewer samples to accurately identify areas of corrosion—averaging 8 and 7 samples respectively, compared to the 29 samples typically needed for random sampling. This stark contrast underscores the superior efficiency and precision of AI-enhanced AS in identifying corrosion, even in localized damage areas.

The second research question (RQ2) explored the impact of various sampling strategy configurations on the efficiency and outcomes of AS in NDT. Through examining different machine learning model configurations, the research demonstrated how specific combinations, particularly RF+GPR and LR+GPR, significantly influence the effectiveness and resource demands of AS. These configurations not only reduced the number of necessary samples but also showcased remarkable precision and reliability, contrasting the variability and unpredictability associated with traditional random sampling methods.

In conclusion, the integration of AI-driven adaptive sampling with NDT marks a significant leap forward in structural health monitoring, providing a scalable, efficient, and precise approach to corrosion detection. This advancement aligns with sustainable construction practices and the goals of a circular economy by minimizing the need for extensive sampling and promoting infrastructure longevity through timely and accurate detection of corrosion. The study contributes a valuable framework for future research aimed at optimizing condition assessments, reinforcing the importance of AI in enhancing the sustainability and efficiency of construction and infrastructure maintenance.

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